

The Least Σ -jump Inversion Theorem for n -families

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Abstract: Studying the Σ -reducibility of families introduced by [Kalimullin and Puzarenko 2009] we show that for every set $X \geq_T \emptyset'$ there is a family of sets \mathcal{F} which is the Σ -least countable family whose Σ -jump is Σ -equivalent to $X \oplus \overline{X}$. This fact will be generalized for the class of n -families (families of families of ... of sets).

Key Words: jump of structure, enumeration jump, Σ -jump, Σ -reducibility, countable family, n -family

Category: F.1.1., F.1.2., F.4.1.

1 Introduction

In this paper study a reducibility among families of sets introduced in [Kalimullin and Puzarenko 2009]. We will say that a family $\mathcal{F}_0 \subseteq 2^\omega$ is Σ -reducible to a family $\mathcal{F}_1 \subseteq 2^\omega$ if for every admissible set \mathbb{A}

$$\mathcal{F}_1 \text{ is } \Sigma\text{-definable in } \mathbb{A} \implies \mathcal{F}_0 \text{ is } \Sigma\text{-definable in } \mathbb{A}.$$

A family $\mathcal{F} \subseteq 2^\omega$ is Σ -definable in \mathbb{A} if there is a Σ -formula Φ such that

$$\mathcal{F} = \{\{x \in \omega : \Phi(x, y)\} : y \in Y\},$$

for some Σ -definable subset $Y \subseteq \mathbb{A}$. This reducibility can be reformulated in terms of enumeration operators:

Theorem 1. [Kalimullin and Puzarenko 2009] For families \mathcal{F}_0 and \mathcal{F}_1 , the following conditions are equivalent:

1. $\mathcal{F}_0 \leq_{\Sigma} \mathcal{F}_1$;
2. $\mathcal{F}_0 \cup \{\emptyset\} = \{\Theta(C \oplus B \oplus E(\mathcal{F}_1)) : C \in K_{\mathcal{F}_1}\}$ for some enumeration operator Θ and some set $B \in K_{\mathcal{F}_1}$, where $E(\mathcal{F}) = \{u : \exists X \in \mathcal{F} [D_u \subseteq X]\}$, and $K_{\mathcal{F}_1}$ is the class of sets of the form $\langle n, m \rangle \oplus A_1 \oplus \dots \oplus A_m$, $A_i \in \mathcal{F}_1$.

On the other hand, \leq_{Σ} is a natural extension of the enumeration and Turing reducibilities, since $A \leq_e B \iff \{A\} \leq_{\Sigma} \{B\}$.

Let us highlight that Σ -reducibility among families is equivalent to the Σ -definability relation between special structures $\mathfrak{M}_{\mathcal{F}}$ [Kalimullin and Puzarenko 2009]. See the end of this section for the detailed definition of $\mathfrak{M}_{\mathcal{F}}$. Following [Montalbán 2009], [Puzarenko 2009], [Stukachev 2009] we can view the Σ -jumps of families as the jumps of the corresponding structures.

Definition 2. For a structure \mathfrak{M} , define the jump of \mathfrak{M} to be the structure $\mathcal{J}(\mathfrak{M}) = (\mathbb{HFF}(\mathfrak{M}), U_{\Sigma})$, where U_{Σ} is a ternary Σ -predicate on $\mathbb{HFF}(\mathfrak{M})$ universal for the class of all binary Σ -predicates on $\mathbb{HFF}(\mathfrak{M})$, is called a Σ -jump.

For any n -family \mathcal{F} instead of $\mathcal{J}(\mathfrak{M}_{\mathcal{F}})$ we simply write $\mathcal{J}(\mathcal{F})$. The Σ -jump does not depend on the choice of a universal Σ -predicate, up to Σ -equivalence. Furthermore, this Σ -jump on structures having Turing (enumeration) degrees acts in the same way as a Turing (enumeration) jump (see [Puzarenko 2009]). As in the classical case, the Σ -jump operation satisfies the following:

1. $\mathfrak{A} \leq_{\Sigma} \mathcal{J}(\mathfrak{A})$;
2. $\mathfrak{A} \leq_{\Sigma} \mathfrak{B} \Rightarrow \mathcal{J}(\mathfrak{A}) \leq_{\Sigma} \mathcal{J}(\mathfrak{B})$.

We define $\mathcal{J}^n(\mathfrak{A})$ by induction on $n \in \omega$ as follows: $\mathcal{J}^0(\mathfrak{A}) = \mathfrak{A}$, $\mathcal{J}^{n+1}(\mathfrak{A}) = \mathcal{J}(\mathcal{J}^n(\mathfrak{A}))$. It was shown in [Puzarenko 2009] that for any structures \mathfrak{M} and \mathfrak{A} on a finite signature, \mathfrak{M} is Σ_{m+1} -definable in \mathfrak{A} iff $\mathfrak{M} \leq_{\Sigma} \mathcal{J}^m(\mathfrak{A})$.

In [Kalimullin and Puzarenko 2009] some unexpected properties of the family InfCE of all infinite c.e. sets under Σ -reducibility were found. In particular, for a family \mathcal{F} , $\mathcal{F} \leq_{\Sigma}$ InfCE iff the following conditions hold:

1. all sets in \mathcal{F} are c.e.;
2. the index set $\{e : W_e \in \mathcal{F}\}$ is Σ_3^0 ;
3. there exists a computable cover $\widehat{\mathcal{F}}$ of \mathcal{F} , i.e., a computable family $\widehat{\mathcal{F}} \subseteq \mathcal{F}$ such that for any $W \in \mathcal{F}$, we have $W \subseteq V$ for some $V \in \widehat{\mathcal{F}}$.

In this paper, we show that the family InfCE has yet another natural property: InfCE is the Σ -least family among all countable families, whose Σ -jump computes \emptyset'' , i.e., it is the least jump inversion of the Turing degree of \emptyset'' . Moreover, each set $A \geq_T \emptyset'$ has such jump inversion. We show also, that each family $\mathcal{F} \geq_\Sigma \overline{\emptyset}'$ has the Σ -least jump inversion in the extended class of n -families.

The notation and terminology follows from Rogers [Rogers 1967] and [Ershov 1996]. We now formally introduce the generalized notion of n -families and fix the precise way of their coding into the structures.

Definition 3. A 0-family is a subset of ω . For an integer $n > 0$, an n -family is a countable set of $(n - 1)$ -families.

We consider the empty set as an 0-family.

According to [Kalimullin and Faizrahmanov 2016] the definition of computably enumerable n -families is inductive: an n -family \mathcal{F} is computably enumerable if it's elements, $(n - 1)$ -families, are uniformly computably enumerable. We give this definition generalized to an arbitrary admissible set (see [Ershov 1996]):

Definition 4. 1. A Σ_s -formula $\Phi(\bar{z}, y)$, $s \in \omega$, defines a 0-family $X \subseteq \text{Nat}(\mathbb{A})$ in an admissible set \mathbb{A} if there is a tuple $\bar{c} \in \mathbb{A}^k$ such that

$$X = \{m \in \text{Nat}(\mathbb{A}) : \mathbb{A} \models \Phi(\bar{c}, m)\}.$$

In this case, we will write $X = \mathcal{F}_{\Phi(\bar{c})}^{0, \mathbb{A}}$.

2. A Σ_s -formula $\Phi(\bar{z}, x, y)$ defines an 1-family \mathcal{F} , if there are a nonempty Σ_s -subset $E \subseteq \mathbb{A}$ and a tuple $\bar{c} \in \mathbb{A}^k$ such that

$$\mathcal{F} = \{\mathcal{F}_{\Phi(\bar{c}, x)}^{0, \mathbb{A}} : x \in E\}.$$

In this case, we will write $\mathcal{F} = \mathcal{F}_{\Phi(\bar{c}), E}^{1, \mathbb{A}}$.

3. A Σ_s -formula $\Phi(\bar{z}, x_1, \dots, x_{n+2}, y)$ defines an $(n + 2)$ -family \mathcal{F} , if there are a nonempty Σ_s -subset $E \subseteq \mathbb{A}^{n+2}$ and a tuple $\bar{c} \in \mathbb{A}^k$ such that

$$\mathcal{F} = \{\mathcal{F}_{\Phi(\bar{c}, x), E^{(x)}}^{n+1, \mathbb{A}} : x \in \text{Pr}_1(E)\},$$

where

$$\text{Pr}_1(E) = \{x : \exists y_1 \dots \exists y_{n+1} (x, y_1, \dots, y_{n+1}) \in E\},$$

$$E^{(x)} = \{(y_1, \dots, y_{n+1}) : (x, y_1, \dots, y_{n+1}) \in E\}.$$

In this case, we will write $\mathcal{F} = \mathcal{F}_{\Phi(\bar{c}), E}^{n+2, \mathbb{A}}$.

An n -family \mathcal{F} is Σ_s -definable (Σ -definable for the case $s = 1$) in \mathbb{A} if some Σ_s -formula defines \mathcal{F} in \mathbb{A} .

This definition extends the definition given in [Kalimullin and Puzarenko 2009].

We will see below that for the n -families it is enough to consider only special cases of admissible sets, namely, the hereditary finite structures $\mathbb{HFF}(\mathfrak{M})$, where \mathfrak{M} is some algebraic structure. Let M be the domain of \mathfrak{M} and let σ be the language of \mathfrak{M} . The domain of $\mathbb{HFF}(\mathfrak{M})$ is the class of $HF(M)$ of hereditarily finite sets over the set M is defined by induction as follows:

- $H_0(M) = \{\emptyset\}$;
- $H_{n+1}(M) = H_n(M) \cup \mathcal{P}_\omega(H_n(M) \cup M)$;
- $HF(M) = \bigcup_{n < \omega} H_n(M) \cup M$

(where $\mathcal{P}_\omega(X)$ denotes the set of all finite subsets of X).

The hereditarily finite superstructure over \mathfrak{M} is the algebraic structure $\mathbb{HFF}(\mathfrak{M})$ in the signature $\sigma \cup \{U^{(1)}, \in^{(2)}, \emptyset\}$, where $U^{\mathbb{HFF}(\mathfrak{M})} = M$, $\in^{\mathbb{HFF}(\mathfrak{M})} \subseteq (HF(M)) \times (HF(M) \setminus M)$ is the membership relation on $\mathbb{HFF}(\mathfrak{M})$, the constant symbol \emptyset is interpreted as the empty set, and symbols in the signature σ are interpreted in the same way as on \mathfrak{M} .

Following [Kalimullin and Puzarenko 2009], we can code every n -family \mathcal{F} into the admissible superstructure $\mathbb{HFF}(\mathfrak{M}_\mathcal{F})$ over the special structure $\mathfrak{M}_\mathcal{F}$ defined by induction as follows.

- For an arbitrary 0-family A let \mathfrak{M}_A be the structure in the signature $\sigma = \{r, I^1, R^2\}$ with the domain $M_\mathcal{F} = \omega \cup X$, $X = \{x_n : n \in A\}$, such that $R^{\mathfrak{M}_A} = \{\langle n, n+1 \rangle : n \in \omega\} \cup \{\langle x_n, n \rangle : n \in A\}$, $r^{\mathfrak{M}_A} = 0$ and $I^{\mathfrak{M}_A} = \{r^{\mathfrak{M}_A}\}$.
- For an n -family $\mathcal{F} = \{S_i : i \in \omega\}$, $n > 0$, let \mathfrak{M}_A be the structure in the signature $\sigma = \{r, I^1, R^2\}$ with the domain $\bigcup_{k,i} |\mathfrak{M}_{S_i}^k| \cup \{r^{\mathfrak{M}_\mathcal{F}}\}$ (each $\mathfrak{M}_{S_i}^k$ is an isomorphic copy of \mathfrak{M}_{S_i} with a new domain) such that $I^{\mathfrak{M}_\mathcal{F}} = \bigcup_{k,i} I^{\mathfrak{M}_{S_i}^k}$ and

$$R(x, y) \Leftrightarrow x = (\exists k, i) [x = r^{\mathfrak{M}_\mathcal{F}} \ \& \ y = r^{\mathfrak{M}_i^k} \ \vee \ R^{\mathfrak{M}_i^k}(x, y)]$$

for each $x, y \in |\mathfrak{M}_\mathcal{F}|$.

Through this inductive definition, the elements of $I^{\mathfrak{M}_\mathcal{F}}$ are precisely the elements originally denoted as $r^{\mathfrak{M}_A}$ for 0-families $A \in \dots \in \mathcal{F}$. For $i \in I^{\mathfrak{M}_\mathcal{F}}$ we denote the corresponding 0-family by A_i .

It is easy to check that every n -family \mathcal{F} is Σ -definable in $\mathbb{HFF}(\mathfrak{M}_\mathcal{F})$. For example, if $n = 0$ then a 0-family $A \subseteq \omega$ is defined by the formula saying that there is a sequence

$$r^{\mathfrak{M}_\mathcal{F}} = n_0, n_1, n_2, \dots, n_{x+1}, p$$

such that $R(n_i, n_{i+1})$ for all $i \leq x$, and $R(p, n_{x+1})$, $p \neq n_x$. Moreover, it follows from [Kalimullin and Puzarenko 2009] that the Σ -definability of \mathcal{F} is equivalent to the Σ -definability of $\mathfrak{M}_\mathcal{F}$ itself.

Proposition 5. [Kalimullin and Puzarenko 2009] *An n -family \mathcal{F} is Σ -definable in a countable admissible set \mathbb{A} iff the structure $\mathfrak{M}_{\mathcal{F}}$ (and, therefore, $\mathbb{H}\mathbb{F}(\mathfrak{M}_{\mathcal{F}})$) is Σ -definable in \mathbb{A} .*

Under Σ -interpretation of a structure \mathfrak{M} in a signature σ we understand a Σ -definable structure \mathfrak{N} in the language $\sigma \cup \{\sim\}$, where \sim is a new congruence relation on \mathfrak{N} such that $\mathfrak{N}/\sim \cong \mathfrak{M}$.

Definition 6. Let \mathcal{F} be an n -family and \mathfrak{M} be a structure. We say that \mathcal{F} is Σ -reducible to \mathfrak{M} (written $\mathcal{F} \leq_{\Sigma} \mathfrak{M}$) if $\mathfrak{M}_{\mathcal{F}}$ is Σ -definable in $\mathbb{H}\mathbb{F}(\mathfrak{M})$. Similarly, $\mathfrak{M} \leq_{\Sigma} \mathcal{F}$ if \mathfrak{M} is Σ -definable in $\mathbb{H}\mathbb{F}(\mathfrak{M}_{\mathcal{F}})$. If \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{S} are n - and m -families correspondingly we say that \mathcal{F} is Σ -reducible to \mathcal{S} if $\mathcal{F} \leq_{\Sigma} \mathfrak{M}_{\mathcal{S}}$. As usual, the relation \equiv_{Σ} holds in the case of Σ -reductions from the left to the right and from the right to the left.

Note that for an n -family \mathcal{F} and the $(n + 1)$ -family $\{\mathcal{F}\}$ we have $\{\mathcal{F}\} \equiv_{\Sigma} \mathcal{F}$. By this reason we can view an n -family \mathcal{F} as an m -family for $m > n$.

Recall that for the case $n = 0$ the standard notation is

$$Y \oplus A = \{2x : x \in Y\} \cup \{2x + 1 : x \in A\}.$$

If Y is an arbitrary set and \mathcal{F} is an n -family, $n > 0$, then we define the *join* of Y and \mathcal{F} inductively by letting

$$Y \oplus \mathcal{F} = \{Y \oplus \mathcal{S} : \mathcal{S} \in \mathcal{F}\}.$$

For an n -family \mathcal{F} and an integer k , denote by \mathcal{F}^k the n -family $\{k\} \oplus \mathcal{F}$. Clearly, for every integer k and an n -family \mathcal{F} , we have $\mathcal{F} \equiv_{\Sigma} \mathcal{F}^k$. For n -families \mathcal{F}, \mathcal{G} define the n -family

$$\mathcal{F} \oplus \mathcal{G} = \mathcal{F}^0 \cup \mathcal{G}^1.$$

It is easy to see that $\mathcal{F} \leq_{\Sigma} \mathcal{F} \oplus \mathcal{G}$, $\mathcal{G} \leq_{\Sigma} \mathcal{F} \oplus \mathcal{G}$, and

$$\mathcal{F} \leq_{\Sigma} \mathfrak{M}, \mathcal{G} \leq_{\Sigma} \mathfrak{M} \implies \mathcal{F} \oplus \mathcal{G} \leq_{\Sigma} \mathfrak{M}$$

for every structure \mathfrak{M} .

2 Jump and jump inversion on n -families

Example 1. ([Puzarenko 2009]). For a 0-family A the jump $\mathcal{J}(A)$ is Σ -equivalent to $\mathfrak{M}_{J(A)}$, where $J(A)$ is the the enumeration jump of A :

$$J(A) = K(A) \oplus \overline{K(A)} \text{ and } K(A) = \{n : n \in \Phi_n(A)\},$$

where $\{\Phi_n\}_{n \in \omega}$ is an effective enumeration of the enumeration operators.

Example 2. It is easy to check that for the family InfCE of all infinite c.e. sets we have $\mathcal{J}(\text{InfCE}) \equiv_{\Sigma} J(J(\emptyset)) \equiv_e \overline{\emptyset}''$. Indeed, $\overline{\emptyset}''$ is computably isomorphic to $\{n : W_n \text{ is infinite}\}$, and a c.e. set W_n is infinite if and only if the (uniformly) computable set

$$V_n = \{s : W_{n,s} \neq W_{n,s+1}\}$$

is infinite, and so, if and only if $F \subseteq V_n$ for some $F \in \text{InfCE}$. The predicate $F \subseteq V_n$ can be recognized by $J(F)$.

The inverse reduction $\mathcal{J}(\text{InfCE}) \leq_{\Sigma} J(J(\emptyset))$ is obvious.

Therefore, the family InfCE is a jump inversion of $J(J(\emptyset))$, i.e., $\mathcal{J}(\text{InfCE}) \equiv_{\Sigma} J(J(\emptyset))$.

Proposition 7. *The 1-family InfCE is the the least jump inversion for the 0-family $J(J(\emptyset))$ among countable structures, i.e., $J(J(\emptyset)) \leq_{\Sigma} \mathcal{J}(\mathfrak{M})$ implies $\text{InfCE} \leq_{\Sigma} \mathfrak{M}$.*

Proof. Suppose $J(J(\emptyset)) \leq_{\Sigma} \mathcal{J}(\mathfrak{M})$ for some countable \mathfrak{M} . Then the index set $\{n : W_n \text{ is infinite}\}$ is Σ_2 -definable in $\text{HIF}(\mathfrak{M})$. Then there is Δ_0 -formula Φ such that

$$W_n \text{ is infinite} \iff \text{HIF}(\mathfrak{M}) \models \exists a \forall b \Phi(n, a, b).$$

Then the sequence

$$V_{n,a} = \begin{cases} W_n, & \text{if } \text{HIF}(\mathfrak{M}) \models \forall b \Phi(n, a, b); \\ \omega, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases}$$

exhausting all infinite c.e. sets can be determined by the Σ -predicate

$$x \in V_{n,a} \iff x \in W_n \vee x \in \omega \ \& \ \exists b \neg \Phi(n, a, b).$$

This allows us to prove the reducibility $\text{InfCE} \leq_{\Sigma} \mathfrak{M}$ for every countable \mathfrak{M} such that $J(J(\emptyset)) \leq_{\Sigma} \mathcal{J}(\mathfrak{M})$.

Now, our goal is to extend Proposition 7 for arbitrary n -family \mathcal{F} . For each n -family \mathcal{F} , recursively define an $(n+1)$ -family $\mathcal{E}(\mathcal{F})$:

$$\mathcal{E}(\mathcal{F}) = \begin{cases} \mathcal{H}_1 \cup \{\{2x\} : x \in A\}, & \text{if } n = 0 \text{ and } \mathcal{F} = A \subseteq \omega, \\ \mathcal{H}_{n+1} \cup \{\mathcal{E}(\mathcal{S}) : \mathcal{S} \in \mathcal{F}^0\}, & \text{if } n > 0, \end{cases}$$

where $\mathcal{H}_1 = \{\{2x, 2x+1\} : x \in \omega\}$ and $\mathcal{H}_{n+1} = \{\mathcal{H}_n\}$. This is similar to some definitions that appear in [Kalimullin and Puzarenko 2009] and [Faizrahmanov and Kalimullin 2016 (a), (b)].

According to the following theorem we will call $\mathcal{E}(\mathcal{F})$ as the *least Σ -jump inversion for \mathcal{F}* (meaning that in fact it is an inversion of $J(\emptyset) \oplus \mathcal{F}$).

Theorem 8. For any n -family \mathcal{F} the $(n + 1)$ -family $\mathcal{E}(\mathcal{F})$ is the least jump inversion of \mathcal{F} . Namely,

- 1) $\mathcal{F} \leq_{\Sigma} \mathcal{J}(\mathcal{E}(\mathcal{F}))$;
- 2) for each countable structure \mathfrak{B} of a finite signature, $\mathcal{E}(\mathcal{F}) \leq_{\Sigma} \mathfrak{B}$ if $\mathcal{F} \leq_{\Sigma} \mathcal{J}(\mathfrak{B})$.
- 3) $\mathcal{J}(\mathcal{E}(\mathcal{F})) \leq_{\Sigma} J(\emptyset) \oplus \mathcal{F}$.

Proof. 1) Since we can view each n -family as an m -family for $m > n$, without loss of generality we assume that $n > 0$. Let $\mathbb{A} = \text{HF}(\mathfrak{M}_{\mathcal{E}(\mathcal{F})})$.

It is easy to see that there is a Σ_2 -formula Φ such that

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{A} \models \Phi(x_1, \dots, x_n, m) &\iff \exists i [R^{\mathbb{A}}(x_n, i) \& I^{\mathbb{A}}(i) \& A_i = \{2m\}] \iff \\ &\exists t [R^{\mathbb{A}}(x_n, i) \& I^{\mathbb{A}}(i) \& 2m \in A_i \& 2m + 1 \notin A_i], \end{aligned}$$

where each A_i , for $i \in I^{\mathfrak{M}_{\mathcal{E}(\mathcal{F})}}$, is from the definition of $\mathfrak{M}_{\mathcal{E}(\mathcal{F})}$. Then for the Σ -subset

$$E = \{(x_1, \dots, x_n) : R^{\mathbb{A}}(r^{\mathbb{A}}, x_1) \& R^{\mathbb{A}}(x_i, x_{i+1}) \text{ for } 1 \leq i < n\}$$

of \mathbb{A}^n we will have

$$\mathcal{F} = \{\mathcal{F}_{\Phi(x), E(x)}^{n, \mathbb{A}} : x \in \text{Pr}_1(E)\}.$$

Hence $\mathcal{F} \leq_{\Sigma_2} \mathcal{E}(\mathcal{F})$ so that $\mathcal{F} \leq_{\Sigma} \mathcal{J}(\mathcal{E}(\mathcal{F}))$.

2) Let an n -family \mathcal{F} is Σ -reducible to $\mathcal{J}(\mathfrak{B})$ for some structure \mathfrak{B} . Hence $\mathcal{F}^0 \leq_{\Sigma} \mathcal{J}(\mathfrak{B})$. Fix a Σ_2 -subset $E \subseteq \text{HF}(\mathfrak{B})$, Σ_2 -formula Θ and a tuple $\bar{c} \in \text{HF}^m(\mathfrak{B})$ such that

$$\mathcal{F}^0 = \{\mathcal{F}_{\Theta(\bar{c}, x), E(x)}^{n, \text{HF}(\mathfrak{B})} : x \in \text{Pr}_1(E)\}.$$

Let Ψ be a Δ_0 -formula such that the Σ_2 -formula $\exists a \forall b \Psi(a, b, \bar{c}, x_1, \dots, x_n, k)$ defines the Σ_2 -predicate

$$\{(x_1, \dots, x_n) \in E^n : \Theta(\bar{c}, x_1, \dots, x_n, k)\}$$

in $\text{HF}(\mathfrak{B})$. Then there is a Σ -formula Φ such that for every $x_1, \dots, x_n, a \in \text{HF}(\mathfrak{B})$ and $k \in \omega$ we have $\text{HF}(\mathfrak{B}) \models \Phi(x_1, \dots, x_n, \langle a, k \rangle, 2k)$ and

$$\text{HF}(\mathfrak{B}) \models \Phi(x_1, \dots, x_n, \langle a, k \rangle, 2k+1) \iff \text{HF}(\mathfrak{B}) \models \exists b \neg \Psi(a, b, \bar{c}, x_1, \dots, x_n, k).$$

It is easy to see that for every $x_1, \dots, x_n, a \in \text{HF}(\mathfrak{B})$ and $k \in \omega$ we have

$$\mathcal{F}_{\Phi(x_1, \dots, x_n, \langle a, k \rangle)}^{0, \text{HF}(\mathfrak{B})} = \{2k\} \iff \text{HF}(\mathfrak{B}) \models \forall b \Psi(a, b, \bar{c}, x_1, \dots, x_n).$$

Thus, $\mathcal{E}(\mathcal{F}) = \{\mathcal{F}_{\Phi(x), C(x)}^{n+1, \mathbb{H}\mathbb{F}(\mathfrak{B})} : x \in \text{Pr}_1(C)\} \cup \mathcal{H}_{n+1}$ for the Σ -set

$$C = \{(x_1, \dots, x_n, \langle a, k \rangle) \in \mathbb{H}\mathbb{F}(\mathfrak{B}) : x_1, \dots, x_n, a \in HF(\mathfrak{B}), k \in \omega\}.$$

Therefore $\mathcal{E}(\mathcal{F}) \leq_{\Sigma} \mathfrak{B}$.

3) By Theorem 1 from [Stukachev 2009] there is a countable structure \mathfrak{B} such that $J(\emptyset) \oplus \mathcal{F} \equiv_{\Sigma} \mathcal{J}(\mathfrak{B})$. Since $\mathcal{F} \leq_{\Sigma} \mathcal{J}(\mathfrak{B})$ we have $\mathcal{E}(\mathcal{F}) \leq_{\Sigma} \mathfrak{B}$. Therefore, $\mathcal{J}(\mathcal{E}(\mathcal{F})) \leq_{\Sigma} \mathcal{J}(\mathfrak{B}) \leq_{\Sigma} J(\emptyset) \oplus \mathcal{F}$. This ends the proof.

Corollary 9. *For every pair of n -families \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{G}*

1. $\mathcal{F} \leq_{\Sigma} \mathcal{G} \implies \mathcal{E}(\mathcal{F}) \leq_{\Sigma} \mathcal{E}(\mathcal{G})$;
2. $\mathcal{E}(\mathcal{F} \oplus \mathcal{G}) \equiv_{\Sigma} \mathcal{E}(\mathcal{F}) \oplus \mathcal{E}(\mathcal{G})$.

Proof. Part 1 follows from the fact that $\mathcal{F} \leq_{\Sigma} \mathcal{G} \leq_{\Sigma} \mathcal{J}(\mathcal{E}(\mathcal{G}))$. Part 2 follows from the fact that $\mathcal{E}(A \oplus B) = \mathcal{H}_1 \cup \{\{2x : x \in A \oplus B\}\} = \mathcal{H}_1 \cup \{\{4x : x \in A\} \cup \{\{4x + 2 : x \in B\}\} \equiv_{\Sigma} \{X \oplus Y : X \in \mathcal{E}(A) \ \& \ Y \in \mathcal{E}(B)\} = \mathcal{E}(A) \oplus \mathcal{E}(B)$.

By the definition of $\mathcal{E}(\cdot)$ the least double jump inversion $\mathcal{E}^2(\mathcal{F}) = \mathcal{E}(\mathcal{E}(\mathcal{F}))$ of an n -family \mathcal{F} is an $(n + 2)$ -family. But we know from [Faizrahmanov and Kalimullin 2016 (a)] that under Turing reducibility of presentations of n -families the least double jump is an $(n + 1)$ -family. For example, for the case of 0-family A the least double jump $\mathcal{E}^2(A)$ has the same Turing degrees of presentations of $\mathfrak{M}_{\mathcal{E}^2(A)}$ as the degrees of presentations of $\mathfrak{M}_{\mathcal{G}}$, where \mathcal{G} is the 1-family

$$\mathcal{G} = \{F \subseteq \omega : F \text{ is finite}\} \cup \{\overline{\{x\}} : x \in A\}.$$

Below we show that for the case of Σ -reducibility we can not have an equivalence between $\mathcal{E}^2(\mathcal{F})$ and some $(n + 1)$ -family even for $n = 0$.

Theorem 10. *For a set A and a 1-family \mathcal{G} we have*

$$\mathcal{J}(\mathcal{G}) \leq_{\Sigma} J(\emptyset) \oplus \mathcal{E}(A) \implies \mathcal{J}(\mathcal{G}) \leq_{\Sigma} J(\emptyset)$$

and, therefore, $\mathcal{J}(\mathcal{G}) \not\equiv_{\Sigma} J(\emptyset) \oplus \mathcal{E}(A)$. Thus, no 1-family can be a double jump inversion of A .

Proof. (Sketch) Let us look at the jump of $\mathcal{J}(\mathcal{G}) = \mathcal{J}(\mathfrak{M}_{\mathcal{G}})$ for 1-families \mathcal{G} . Because of [Kalimullin and Puzarenko 2009], all Σ -predicates in $\mathfrak{M}_{\mathcal{G}}$ can be encoded in the sets

$$A_1 \oplus A_2 \oplus \dots \oplus A_m \oplus E(\mathcal{G}),$$

where $A_i \in \mathcal{G}$ and the set $E(\mathcal{G}) = \{u : (\exists A \in \mathcal{G}) [D_u \subseteq A]\}$ codes the \exists -theory of $\mathfrak{M}_{\mathcal{G}}$. But the family of enumeration jumps of these sets cannot fully represent the jump of the whole \mathcal{G} since we need to keep the information when a jump for

a tuple A_1, \dots, A_m is an extension of the jump for a tuple A_1, \dots, A_m, A_{m+1} . In fact, the jump $\mathcal{J}(\mathcal{G})$ (up to Σ -equivalence) can be viewed as a structure coding the jumps of the sets $A \in E(\mathcal{G}) \oplus \mathcal{G}$ extended by the similar coding of the jumps of elements of the \oplus -closure of $E(\mathcal{G}) \oplus \mathcal{G}$ with an additional binary operation which maps coding places of $J(X), J(Y)$ to the coding places of $J(X \oplus Y)$. Each coding instance should be generated by this binary operation from the instances coding jumps of the elements of $E(\mathcal{G}) \oplus \mathcal{G}$. The last instances should be marked by a special predicate. We omit technical details and a technical verification. Informally, such structure allows to compute all Σ -types in $\mathfrak{M}_{\mathcal{G}}$, and, therefore, to build an isomorphic copy of the original $\mathcal{J}(\mathcal{G})$.

Suppose that

$$\mathcal{J}(\mathcal{G}) \leq_{\Sigma} J(\emptyset) \oplus \mathcal{E}(A) = \{J(\emptyset) \oplus \{2n, 2n + 1\} : n \in \omega\} \cup \{J(\emptyset) \oplus \{2n\} : n \in A\}$$

as witnessed by some Σ -formula Φ . For simplicity we assume that Φ has no parameters.

Note that the structure $\mathfrak{M}_{J(\emptyset) \oplus \mathcal{E}(A)}$ is bi-embeddable with $\mathfrak{M}_{J(\emptyset) \oplus \mathcal{H}_1} \leq_{\Sigma} J(\emptyset)$, where

$$J(\emptyset) \oplus \mathcal{H}_1 = \{J(\emptyset) \oplus \{2n, 2n + 1\} : n \in \omega\}.$$

Moreover, they are *densely* bi-embeddable in the sense that for every finite substructure $\mathfrak{M}_0 \subseteq \mathfrak{M}_{J(\emptyset) \oplus \mathcal{E}(A)}$ there is a substructure $\mathfrak{M}_0 \subseteq \mathfrak{M}_1 \subseteq \mathfrak{M}_{J(\emptyset) \oplus \mathcal{E}(A)}$ such that $\mathfrak{M}_1 \cong \mathfrak{M}_{J(\emptyset) \oplus \mathcal{H}_1}$, and vice versa. Considering the same formula Φ in $\text{HIF}(\mathfrak{M}_{J(\emptyset) \oplus \mathcal{H}_1})$ we get a structure $\mathcal{L} \leq_{\Sigma} J(\emptyset)$ densely bi-embeddable with $\mathcal{J}(\mathcal{G})$. But $J(X) \subseteq J(Y)$ implies $J(X) = J(Y)$ so that this is possible only if $\mathcal{J}(\mathcal{G}) \cong \mathcal{L}$. Hence, $\mathcal{J}(\mathcal{G}) \leq_{\Sigma} J(\emptyset)$.

In the case when Φ has parameters we should change \mathcal{H}_1 by a 1-family in the form

$$\mathcal{H}_1 \cup \{n_1\} \cup \{n_2\} \cup \dots \cup \{n_k\}$$

for appropriate choice of $n_1, \dots, n_k \in A$ (depending on the given parameters of Φ) preserving the dense bi-embeddability property up to finitely many constants.

To prove the second part of the theorem suppose that $\mathcal{J}(\mathcal{G}) \equiv_{\Sigma} J(\emptyset) \oplus \mathcal{E}(A)$. Then by the first part $\mathcal{J}(\mathcal{G}) \leq_{\Sigma} \mathcal{J}(\emptyset)$. On the other hand, by Theorem 8

$$A \leq_{\Sigma} \mathcal{J}(\mathcal{E}(A)) \leq_{\Sigma} \mathcal{J}^2(\mathcal{G}) \leq_{\Sigma} \mathcal{J}^2(\emptyset) \equiv_{\Sigma} J^2(\emptyset),$$

so that $A \in \Sigma_3^0$.

Since $\mathcal{J}(\mathcal{E}^2(A)) \equiv_{\Sigma} J(\emptyset) \oplus \mathcal{E}(A)$, by Theorem 8 we have also the following corollary:

Corollary 11. *For a set a set $A \notin \Sigma_3^0$ there is no 1-family \mathcal{G} such that $\mathcal{G} \equiv_{\Sigma} \mathcal{E}^2(A)$, so that the least double jump inversion of a 0-family A can not be replaced by a 1-family.*

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